

Integrating deep learning and meshing techniques to perform 3D reconstruction of patient-specific carotid bifurcation with plaque classification

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Abstract— One of the diseases in human cardiovascular system is carotid artery stenosis (CAS) and its early detection is very important in order to prevent potentially deteriorating consequences. Ultrasound (US) imaging is usually the initial recommended CAS diagnostic examination technique, because of a noninvasive procedure without ionizing radiation. This examination can identify atherosclerotic plaque components in order to pre-estimate the risk of cardiovascular disease and ensure appropriate preventive, therapeutic, or surgical treatment. However, conventional 2D US imaging has technical limitations in observing the complicated 3D shapes and asymmetric vasodilation of bifurcations. In this study an integrated approach is presented that is capable of performing 3D reconstruction of patient-specific carotid bifurcation from US images. Deep learning techniques are used to segment the regions of interest including lumen and arterial wall areas, as well as plaque types. Afterwards, meshing techniques are applied to create the 3D geometry and hexagonal mesh of finite elements. The characterization of carotid plaques in three dimensions could improve investigations of the changes of plaque morphology, geometry and its distribution and these can provide important information about the effects of anti-atherosclerotic therapies. The generated models can also be used to perform further numerical simulations, involving blood flow, stenting implantation or plaque progression.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deep learning techniques have emerged as a promising tool for the automatic classification and interpretation of medical image data. In this study, deep learning techniques are combined with meshing strategies to perform 3D reconstruction of patient-specific carotid bifurcation together

with characterization of plaque components within the arterial wall.

II. METHODS AND RESULTS

The proposed approach was validated in [1] for the case of lumen reconstruction. In this study, a different clinical dataset was used to perform full reconstruction of carotid bifurcation, including plaque classification. The U-Net based deep convolutional network [2] was used to segment the regions of lumen and arterial wall and to perform classification of atherosclerotic plaque components (lipid core, fibrous and calcified tissue). This data is then processed by the reconstruction software to generate patient-specific 3D mesh. The reconstructed carotid bifurcation is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The reconstructed patient-specific carotid bifurcation. A – Whole reconstructed mesh with transparent wall; B – transversal cross-sections; C – augmented part of the mesh with plaque.

With the reconstruction software presented in this study, it is possible to obtain volume information in three dimensions and perform the visualization of vascular structures in different planes from different angles.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Djukic, B. Arsic, S. Djorovic, N. Filipovic, and I. Koncar, “Validation of the machine learning approach for 3D reconstruction of carotid artery from ultrasound imaging,” Proc. - IEEE 20th Int. Conf. Bioinforma. Bioeng. BIBE 2020, pp. 789–794, 2020, doi: 10.1109/BIBE50027.2020.00134.
- [2] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, “U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation,” 2015, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-24574-4_28.

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